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Techno-economic modelling of the Baltic CCUS onshore scenario for the cement industry supported by CLEANKER project

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Abstract

Baltic transboundary CCUS scenario includes CO₂ emissions from six largest CO₂ producers from Estonia and Latvia, CO₂ mineral carbonation of Estonian oil shale ash, pipeline transport of captured CO₂ and its storage in the North-Blidene structure in the western Latvia. HeidelbergCement owned Kunda Nordic Cement plant, three Eesti Energia power plants (Eesti, Balti and Auvere PP), VKG Energia North Thermal PP and Latvenergo TEC-2 PP compose cluster of CO₂ emitters.

Estonian OSA could be used as an effective sorbent in the CO₂-mineralization process, using CO₂ from flue gas and producing precipitated CaCO₃ (PCC). Techno-economic modelling of scenario includes mineral carbonation of 0.42 Mt CO₂ using 3.8 Mt of fresh OSA and pipeline transport of about 6.33 Mt CO₂ captured annually by five Estonian and one Latvian plant for storage in Cambrian Deimena Formation reservoir sandstones at the depth of 1035-1150 m in the North-Blidene structure. Average optimistic storage capacity of about 270 Mt allows to plan CCUS project for 30 years.

Annually 6.8 Mt CO₂ could be captured, transported and injected, including 6 Mt CO₂ avoided using transport and storage and 0.42 Mt CO₂ avoided using MC of Estonian OSA. During 30 years nearly 204 Mt CO₂ will be captured, used and stored, while 193 Mt CO₂ could be avoided. At the price of EEAP of 40 €/t CO₂ and 50 €/t PCC the CCUS scenario could be beneficial for three Eesti Energia and Latvenergo TEC-2 power plants. For the KNC and VKG Energia plants without CO₂ use options, the higher EEAP of about 48-50 €/t CO₂ is needed to cover all CCUS costs including capture, compression, transport, storage and monitoring. The transport and storage costs are distance-dependant, as pipelines are the most expensive part of the transport, storage and monitoring costs.

Keywords: CCUS, economic modeling, CO₂ emissions, storage, pipelines, mineral carbonation, carbon tax, oil shale ash, cement plant

1. Introduction

The EU Horizon 2020 project CLEANKER is aimed on Ca-looping capture of CO₂ emissions produced by cement industry. CLEANKER project also includes techno-economic modelling of CO₂ transport, storage, and utilization

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scenarios. One of these scenarios is a Baltic regional scenario, which includes Kunda Nordic Tsement (KNC), main Estonian cement producer, and CO₂ mineral carbonation of Estonian oil shale ash, as possible CO₂ use option [1].

Total CO₂ emissions per capita (14.2 t) produced in Estonia in 2019 was at the second place in Europe (after Luxembourg) and at the 19th in the world. The total fossil fuel CO₂ emissions produced in 2019 was 18.50 Mt [2]. Nearly 50% of these emissions (7.9 Mt) were produced by eight largest emission sources, including four power plants (three Narva plants, owned by Eesti Energia and one VKG Energia plant), three plants producing oil from Estonian local oil shale and KNC [3]. CO₂ emissions produced in Estonia in 2019 were lower for 5 Mt per year compared to 2018, after closing of some blocks at the power plants owned by Eesti Energia company. The company explained this by increasing cost for energy production caused by increased EEAP (CO₂ tax) from EU ETS. Now Estonia is importing energy from the neighboring countries, resulting into CO₂ leakage to these countries. Considering new trends in energy production in Estonia, corresponding to Paris Climate Agreements targets and European zero carbon targets, CO₂ emissions produced in 2019 were used for techno-economic modelling of the Baltic CCUS scenario.

Different approaches are used to estimate costs of CCS projects. In the FP6 EU GeoCapacity project stochastic analysis of costs using Monte-Carlo simulation in DSS (Decision Support System) were used, based on the collected GIS [4]. In Australian Power Generation Technology Report [5], the University of Sydney estimated the cost for transport and storage of CO₂ from power plants in Australia using information collected from Australian stakeholders.

Nomenclature			
BEC	Bare erected cost for pipeline, booster, wells and storage facilities	EU ETS FOM	European Union Emission Trading System Annual fixed operating and maintaining cost
CAPEX/ t_{CO_2}	Total capital expenses per one tonne of CO ₂ injected/avoided	KNC MC	Kunda Nordic Tsement plant in Estonia Mineral Carbonation
CCR	Capital charge rate (%)	MVEX/ t_{CO_2}	Monitoring and verification expenses per one tonne of CO ₂ injected/avoided
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage		
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage	O&M	Operational and Maintenance cost
CFBC	Circulated Fluidized Bed Combustion Technology	OPEX/ t_{CO_2}	Operational and maintenance expenses per one tonne of CO ₂ injected/avoided
COST _{energy}	Annual energy cost	OS	Oil shale
COST _{mv}	Annual monitoring and verification cost	OSA	Oil shale ash
COST _{oper}	Annual onsite operating costs	PCC	Precipitated Calcium Carbonate
COST _{total} / t_{CO_2}	Total costs per one tonne of CO ₂ injected	PP	Power Plant
Decom	Decommissioning Cost	TPC	Total Plant Cost
EEAP	CO ₂ Emission Allowance Price in EU ETS	T&S	Transport and Storage
ENEREX/ t_{CO_2}	Energy expenses per one tonne of CO ₂ injected	VSP	Vertical seismic profiling

1. Data and methods

CO₂ emissions produced in 2019 and reported in EU ETS were used for CCUS scenario [3]. Methodology developed by CLEANKER project for techno-economic modelling of CCUS scenarios was applied [6]. All geological and technical data needed for scenario modelling were collected into ArcGIS based system created for the CLEANKER project. In this study we have combined and incorporated approaches and data collected in the FP6 EU GeoCapacity Project [4] and Australian Power Generation Technology Report [5]. Building block datasets from this report in the form of figures, tables and equations were used to estimate costs and performance for the pipeline transportation and geological storage of CO₂. Spatial data were collected and maps were constructed using ArcGIS platform, version 10.6. The costs of all CO₂ storage and transport elements are calculated in total and specifically for the all CO₂ producers, proportionally to their CO₂ flow. As three largest Eesti Energia plants are involved into the CCUS scenario and CO₂ mineral carbonation, their costs and benefits often calculated together, while distribution of

costs between plants depends on distances to the CO₂ mineral carbonation plant, CO₂ storage site and on their CO₂ flow share in total emissions produced by Eesti Energia PPs. The average cost per tonne of CO₂ injected, or per tonne of CO₂ avoided for the project duration (30-years) is calculated using below formulas, applied in [5] and updated for CLEANKER project in [6]:

$$\text{CAPEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\text{CCR} \times \text{TPC} + \text{FOM}}{\text{CO}_2 \text{ injected}}, (\text{€}/t \text{ CO}_2), \quad \text{OPEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\text{CCR} \times \text{COST}_{\text{oper}}}{\text{CO}_2 \text{ injected}}, (\text{€}/t \text{ CO}_2)$$

$$\text{MVEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\text{COST}_{\text{mv}}}{\text{CO}_2 \text{ injected}}, (\text{€}/t \text{ CO}_2), \quad \text{ENEREX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\text{COST}_{\text{energy}}}{\text{CO}_2 \text{ injected}}, (\text{€}/t \text{ CO}_2)$$

$$\text{COST}_{\text{total}}/t_{\text{CO}_2} = \text{CAPEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} + \text{OPEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} + \text{MVEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2} + \text{ENERGEX}/t_{\text{CO}_2}; \quad \text{TPC} = \text{BEC} + \text{Decom} + \text{interest}$$

For this scenario CCR is taken as 8% and interest paid during construction is 1.5%. It is assumed that the annual fixed O&M cost is 1% for pipelines, 2% for wells and 4% for the booster pumps and storage facilities. Annual onsite operating costs, which includes design, engineering, environmental assessment, project/site supervision, management, logistics fees and equipment/project contingencies, is taken as 40% from BEC, and Decom is 25% from BEC. It is considered that Decom occurs in the two years following the end of the project and may include costs for site remediation and equipment dismantling [5]. For estimation of the total CCUS scenario costs and revenues we took the cost of CO₂ capture (25.5 €/t CO₂) using oxyfuel CO₂ capture and cost for compression (2.8 €/t CO₂) calculated earlier for Estonian-Latvian crossborder scenario in EU GeoCapacity project [4].

2. CO₂ emission sources

Kunda Nordic Tsement plant (KNC) owned by HeidelbergCement Group is located in the northern Estonia about 80-90 km west of the largest in the country Eesti and Balti PPs. Nearly all cement consumption in Estonia is covered by the KNC, operating a wet cement production process. Its main energy source is oil shale. The main raw materials that it uses are clay, limestone and oil shale ash. Clay and limestone are mined in nearby quarries. The Supervisory Board of KNC has decided to stop the clinker production in Kunda in March 2020. The decision was taken due to the significant increase in the cost of CO₂, highly affecting the Kunda plant with its high CO₂ emission due to the old production technology. The company decided to continue as a cement grinding plant with sales and distribution of cement to its customers. Production of crushed limestone will continue in Kunda. The clinker is sourced now from other producers and transported to the Kunda plant by ship [7].

Three largest in Estonia PPs (Eesti, Balti and Auvere) are owned by state-owned company Eesti Energia. They are called the Narva PPs, because of their location near Narva town in Estonia, near the border with Leningrad Region, Russia. Before 2019, Narva PPs generated about 95% of the total power production in Estonia. The complex is owned and operated by Enefit Energiatootmine AS, a subsidiary of Eesti Energia [8].

The **Eesti PP** is located roughly 20 km west-south of Narva. As of the end of 2005, Eesti PP had installed power capacity 1,615 MW and thermal capacity 84 MW. The plant had initially 16 boilers and eight 200 MWe steam turbines, from which 14 boilers and seven turbines were in service. In 2003, the Unit 8 was reconstructed to use the CFBC technology. In 2019 using old PC technology units were shut down and only reconstructed Unit 8 is working now. The **Balti PP** is located 5 km south-west of Narva. At the end of 2005, Balti PP had an installed power capacity 765 MW and thermal capacity 400 MW. In 2003, the Unit 11 was reconstructed to use the CFBC technology, which is more efficient and environmental-friendly (lower SO₂ and CO₂ emissions) than PC technology. In 2019 the old units with PC technology were closed and only Unit 11 is working now. The **Auvere PP** is located in Auvere village in Ida-Virumaa, Estonia. Auvere PP is the newest PP built in Estonia on oil shale and biomass, which was completed mainly in 2015. It has a capacity of 300 MW. Auvere PP uses CFBC technology and up to 50% of the OS can be replaced by biomass used in the plant. The total investment amounted to 610 M€. The PP was built by General Electric. The construction contract was concluded in early 2011 and the station was taken over in mid-2018 [8].

VKG Energia Northern Thermal PP (Põhja SEJ) is located in Järve district of Kohtla-Järve, 4 km from the Gulf of Finland. VKG Energia OÜ is a subsidiary of Viru Keemia Grupp AS (VKG AS), the largest shale oil producer in Estonia. In 2020 VKG Energia Northern Thermal PP had six boilers with a total thermal input of 379 MW and five

turbines with a total capacity of 87 MW for electricity generation. Fuels used in North SEJ are: generator gas, semi-coking gas, oil shale and ash-rich fuel. The latter is mixed with oil shale before being given into the boiler [9].

Latvenergo TEC-2 thermal PP is the largest thermal PP in Latvia located in Acone, Salaspils region. The plant has five units with total electrical power 881 MW and total heat capacity of 1124 MW. The first power unit was commissioned in 1975 and the last in 2009. It is operated by Latvian state-owned power company A/S Latvenergo. The PP has now been fully reconstructed.

3. CO₂ use for mineral carbonation

In 2018 four largest Estonian enterprises have mined about 16 Mt of oil shale, which was used for production of energy, heat and shale oil and some other chemical products. During these processes about 9.4 Mt of oil shale ash were produced, including more than 7 Mt by Eesti Energia [10]. In 2019 oil shale production decreased to about 12 Mt and amount of oil shale ash to 6.5 Mt. Eesti Energia plants produced about 3.9 Mt of OS ash in 2019 and used 1.8% (about 120 000 t) for construction and agriculture [11]. It is estimated that 3.81 Mt of OSA produced at three largest Eesti Energia power plants could be used for CO₂ MC annually. In average 250 kg of PCC (precipitated CaCO₃) could be produced from 1t of OSA. Annually $3.81\text{Mt} \cdot 0.25 = 0.95\text{ Mt}$ of PCC could be produced, resulting in 28.6 Mt during 30 years. 110 kg of CO₂ per one ton of OSA could be avoided [12-14]. Annually $3.81\text{ Mt} \cdot 0.11 = 0.42\text{ Mt}$ of CO₂ could be carbonated (avoided), resulting in 12.6 Mt CO₂ avoided per 30 years. Considering that only 90% of CO₂ could be captured from flue gas, 0.47 Mt of produced CO₂ should be used for MC per year.

4. CO₂ storage site

The North Blidene and Blidene structures, the largest prospective for CO₂ storage onshore structures located in the western Latvia, were chosen for the Estonian-Latvian onshore CCUS scenario [1, 15]. Their storage capacity was estimated earlier as 74 and 58Mt CO₂ [16]. The North Blidene is an anticlinal near-fault fold with three domes. The Blidene structure is located in a down-dip block. The Blidene structure is bounded by faults at the north-west and south-east. These two structures are studied by five wells [16]. Contour and 3D structure maps were composed and CO₂ storage capacity of the Blidene and the North Blidene structures (Fig.1) were calculated using improved estimations of all needed parameters. Minimum, maximum and average capacities were estimated for optimistic and conservative cases for both structures (Table 1) using approach presented in [16]. Their total optimistic capacity (min-max/mean) is 186-380/297 Mt, while the conservative capacity was estimated as 33.6-68.0/53.4 Mt. The average optimistic capacity is more than two times higher than the capacity estimated in the previous reports (132 Mt) [16], explained by a larger estimated area and a higher CO₂ density in this study. The average conservative capacity in this study is lower by 2.5 times, explained by the lower storage efficiency applied [1, 15].

Fig. 1. (a) Contour maps of the Deimena Formation in the North Blidene (above) and the Blidene (below) structures. Fault line is indicated with red polyline; (b) 3D structure maps of the Deimena Formation in the North Blidene (above) and the Blidene (below) structures. Both pictures are composed using Golden Surfer 15 software [15].

Table 1. Physical parameters of the North Blidene and Blidene structures in Latvia [15].

Parameters	North Blidene	Blidene
Depth of reservoir top, m	1035-1150	1168-1357
Reservoir thickness, m	48	66
Trap area, km ²	141	62
CO ₂ density, kg/m ³	881	866
Net to gross ratio, %	75	80
Permeability, mD	370-850	370-850
Salinity, g/l	100-114	100-114
T, °C	18	22.9
Storage efficiency factor (S_{eff})	30/4	5/3
Porosity (min-max/avg), %	12.5-25.6/20	13.5-26.6/21
Optimistic CO ₂ storage capacity (min-max/avg), Mt	167-342/267	19-37.5/29.6
Conservative CO ₂ storage capacity (min-max/avg),	22.2-45.5/35.6	11.4-22.5/17.8

5. CCUS scenario

The onshore CCUS scenario includes cluster of CO₂ emissions captured by HeidelbergCement owned Kunda Nordic Cement plant (KNC), Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants owned by Estonian national energy company Eesti Energia, VKG Energia North Thermal Power plant (Põhja SEJ) and Latvenergo TEC-2 PP, the largest CO₂ emitters in Estonia and Latvia (Fig. 2, Table 2). Considering decreased annual emissions in 2019 (Table 2) compared to emissions produced in 2018 [1], it was decided to inject CO₂ into the North Blidene storage site in Latvia, which is the largest one and has smaller depth compared to Blidene site.

Table 2. CO₂ emissions produced, captured and avoided from six Baltic plants.

Location	Estonia					Latvia		Total for Estonian-Latvian scenario
	Company	Heidelberg Cement	Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)		VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latvenergo	
Plant	KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North PP		TEC-2	
Parameters								
CO ₂ emissions produced per year in 2019, Mt	0.55	3.43	0.65	0.92	0.68	6.23	0.90	7.13
CO ₂ use for mineral carbonation, Mt		0.47				0.47		0.47
CO ₂ emission captured per year (95%)	0.52	2.81	0.62	0.87	0.65	5.47	0.85	6.33
CO ₂ emission produced during capture and storage (5%)	0.03	0.14	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.27	0.04	0.32
CO ₂ emissions avoided per year, Mt	0.49	2.67	0.59	0.83	0.61	5.20	0.81	6.01
CO ₂ emissions avoided per 30 years, Mt	14.81	80.14	17.60	24.91	18.41	155.87	24.31	180.2
CO ₂ emissions per year avoided, % from total	8.22	44.48	9.77	13.82	10.22	86.51	13.49	100

Fig. 2. Baltic CCUS scenario for six emission sources, including Kunda Nordic Cement Plant (KNC), 4 Estonian, one Latvian power plants and storage in North Blidene site. CO₂ Mineral Carbonation Plant, using OSA produced by Estonian power plants, is planned near Eesti PP. In total 0.42Mt CO₂ will be bound by OSA and 6.33 Mt stored underground annually. During 30 years of the project about 193 Mt CO₂ could be avoided.

CO₂ emissions will be captured and transported using onshore pipelines to the North Blidene storage site in Latvia. The smaller and dipper Blidene storage site will be left in reserve for the possible new project partners. Local pipelines from the plants to the common pipeline of 710 km lengths will be constructed during two years. The total planned CCUS project duration is 30 years. The average optimistic CO₂ storage capacity of the North Blidene structure (267 Mt) will be enough for all the project time. Annually 6.33 Mt CO₂ captured at the plants will be transported and stored underground in Latvia and additionally 0.42 Mt CO₂ produced by the largest Eesti PP will be captured from flue gas, using mineral carbonation of the produced during energy production OSA. During 30 years nearly 204 Mt CO₂ will be captured, used and stored, while 193 Mt CO₂ could be avoided, considering need of energy for CO₂ capture, compression, transport and storage.

4. Economic modelling

7.1 CO₂ transport infrastructure and costs

The pipelines will be designed using X70 steel and 1500 lb flange rating (rated to 25.5 Mpa upper working pressure) with a maximum allowable working pressure of 15 MPa. The pipeline diameter was determined depending on the distance and flow-rate of CO₂ calculated for the specific scenario according to [5]. The annual flow rate for the local pipelines from KNC and VKG Energia North plants and Latvenergo TEC2 is less than 1 Mt per year and distance to the shared (common) pipeline is 3.5-24 km. Therefore 120-160 mm diameter could be sufficient. The common pipeline is designed for 710 km and 6.33 Mt of CO₂ flow. The cost of pipelines is estimated using Pipelines Capex as a function of transport distance and CO₂ flow-rate [5].

The most expensive transport cost is estimated for Eesti Energia power plants located the most distant from the

storage site and with the largest share in CO₂ flow, both in Estonia and in the Estonian-Latvian project (68%). The most distant location has Balti PP with 19 km distance of local pipeline and 710 km of the common pipeline. The cheapest transport cost is estimated for Latvenergo TEC2 PP, because of its relatively close location to the storage site (25 km to the common pipeline and 160 km along the common pipeline) (Table 3).

Table 3. CO₂ pipelines parameters and costs (*Total for 3 Eesti Energia plants).

Company	Plant	Heidel-berg Cement		Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)		VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latv-energo	Total for Estonian-Latvian scenario
		KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North TPP		TEC2 PP	
Parameters									
Pipeline distance to common pipeline, km/diameter, mm		9/120	12/250	1+12/250	19/200	3.4/120		25/160	
Capital costs for individual pipeline, M€		1.24	2.72	0.72	3.16	0.37	8.21	4.45	12.66
Common part of CO ₂ pipeline, km		615	710	710	710	666		164	710
CAPEX for common pipeline, M€		61.24		603.18*		83.36	747.78	24.06	771.84
Total pipeline CAPEX, M€		62.48		609.78*		83.73	755.99	28.51	784.50
Annual pipeline OPEX, M€		0.63		6.1*		0.84	7.56	0.28	7.85

7.2 CO₂ compression, injection and monitoring costs

Recompression using booster pumps will be needed to keep CO₂ in a dense phase when the pressure will drop below 8 Mpa. The capital cost of booster pumps (CAPEX boosters) is a function of CO₂ flow-rate, and recompression duty is a function of discharge pressure, which is different for various CO₂ flow-rates [5]. Operating cost for boosters is taken as fixed 4% from the capital costs and additionally variable operating cost. The last one will be determined using booster pump duty and energy required for their operation. CO₂ emissions produced during this operation is included in calculation of CO₂ emissions avoided. CO₂ injection costs include well drilling, storage site facilities and monitoring. In total four injection and two monitoring wells are planned for CO₂ storage and monitoring (Table 4). Coring and logging are included for all six wells. Total capital costs for all wells is 17.75 M€.

Cost for onshore 3D seismic survey is calculated using equation $C=MA/1000$, where A is area extent, and M is taken from Table 112 [5]. We took average M given for low cost and high- cost options. For our scenario $C=0.76$ M€, considering 141 km² area of the North Blidene structure, taken for seismic monitoring. Baseline monitoring before injection and every year during injection is needed according to the European regulations [17]. After closure of CO₂ storage site, it will be done annually during three years and then every five years during 30 years [18]. Altogether monitoring should be made and reported 40 times: one baseline before injection, 30 (during injection), and 3+6 (after closure). For 3D seismic survey costs could be $0.76*40=30.4$ M€. For VSP logs in two monitoring wells $0.07*40=2.8$ M€ (Table 5). The most expensive part of the monitoring costs is 3D seismic survey. Additional monitoring expenses in monitoring and injection wells could be covered by 40% O&M costs (on-costs).

7.3 Total costs for CO₂ transport and geological storage for 30 years project

The total average T&S cost of the scenario is 18.4 €/tCO₂ injected (Table 6). This cost is the most expensive for the Eesti Energia PPs, as they need the longest pipelines. The lowest T&S cost of 5.54 €/tCO₂ injected will have Latvenergo TEC2, as they will need the shortest pipelines. The T&S cost is the lowest in Estonia for KNC, as it is located only at the 9+615 km from the storage site (9 km is individual pipeline length and 615 km is the common

pipeline length), while distance from VKG Energia North PP is 3.4+666 km, and for the Eesti Energia PPs is more than at 710 km from the storage site (Table 4).

Table 4. Costs for CO₂ injection and monitoring wells drilling and storage facilities.

Company	Plant	Heidelberg Cement		Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)			VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latv-energo	Total for Estonian-Latvian scenario
		KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North TPP	TEC-2 PP			
Parameters										
Injection wells number		0.33	1.78	0.39	0.55	0.41	3.46	0.54	4.00	
Injection wells CAPEX including coring and logging, M€		0.71	3.86	0.85	1.20	0.89	7.50	1.17	8.67	
Monitoring wells number		0.16	0.89	0.20	0.28	0.20	1.73	0.27	2.00	
Monitoring well CAPEX, including coring and logging, M€		0.36	1.93	0.42	0.60	0.44	3.75	0.58	4.33	
Total CAPEX for all wells, M€		1.07	5.78	1.27	1.80	1.33	11.25	1.75	13.00	
Total CAPEX for injection wells and storage facilities, M€		1.09	5.87	1.29	1.83	1.35	11.43	1.78	13.21	
Total CAPEX for all wells and storage facilities, M€		1.46	7.89	1.73	2.45	1.81	15.35	2.39	17.75	

Table 5. Costs for CO₂ monitoring.

Company	Plant	Heidelberg Cement		Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)			VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latv-energo	Total for Estonian-Latvian scenario
		KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North TPP	TEC-2 PP			
Parameters										
3D seismic survey baseline, M€		0.06	0.34	0.07	0.10	0.08	0.65	0.10	0.76	
VSP logs in 2 wells baseline		0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.07	
3D seismic survey during storage, M€		1.86	10.07	2.21	3.13	2.31	19.60	3.06	22.65	
VSP logs in 2 monitoring wells during storage, M€		0.16	0.88	0.19	0.27	0.20	1.71	0.27	1.97	
3D seismic survey after closure (3+6), M€		0.56	3.02	0.66	0.94	0.69	5.88	0.92	6.80	
VSP logs in 2 monitoring wells after closure (3+6), M€		0.05	0.26	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.51	0.08	0.59	
Annual monitoring costs, M€		0.09	0.49	0.11	0.15	0.11	0.95	0.15	1.09	

To estimate the total project costs and revenues the cost of capture and compression per/t CO₂ avoided calculated in our previous study was adopted [4]. The main revenues for the total CCUS scenario are EEAP (40 €/t CO₂) and additional revenues from CO₂ MC of OSA produced by Eesti Energia PPs (Table 7). For the plants, which will not get zero or negative balance, we calculated EEAP, which will provide zero balance.

Table 6. Total costs for CO₂ transport and storage (* total for 3 Eesti Energia plants).

Company	Plant	Heidelberg Cement		Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)			VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latv-energo	Total for Estonian-Latvian scenario
		KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North TPP	TEC-2 PP			
Parameters										
Total pipeline CAPEX, M€		62.48		609.78*		83.73	755.99	28.51	784.50	
Booster CAPEX, M€		0.65	3.50	0.77	1.09	0.80	6.81	1.06	7.88	
Total CAPEX for all wells, M€		1.07	5.78	1.27	1.80	1.33	11.25	1.75	13.00	
Storage facilities CAPEX, M€		0.37	2.02	0.44	0.63	0.46	3.93	0.61	4.54	
BEC, M€		64.57		627.1*		86.32	777.98	31.93	809.9	
Decommissioning cost (25% from BEC), M€		16.14		156.77*		21.58	194.50	7.98	202.48	
Interest (1.5%)		0.97	9.41	0.00	0.00	1.29	11.67	0.48	12.15	
FOM (annual fixed O&M cost) M€		0.67	6.35	0.06	0.08	0.90	7.78	0.32	8.10	
TPC (Total Plant Cost), M€		81.7	793.3	0.00	0.00	109.2	984.1	40.4	1024.5	
CAPEX, €/tCO₂ injected		13.87		16.22*		14.91	15.82	4.16	14.14	
OPEX total (40%), M€		25.83		250.83*		34.53	311.19	12.77	323.97	
OPEX, €/tCO₂ injected		3.98		4.66*		4.28	4.55	1.20	4.07	
MVEX, M€		0.09	0.49	0.11	0.15	0.11	0.95	0.15	1.09	
MVEX, €/tCO₂ injected		0.17	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.17	
ENEREX), M€		0.0002	0.0012	0.0003	0.0004	0.0003	0.0023	0.0004	0.0027	
ENEREX, €/tCO₂ injected		0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	
COSTtotal, €/tCO₂ injected		18.02		21.06*		19.36	20.54	5.54	18.38	

7.4 CO₂ mineral carbonation costs and revenues

According to the published data the cost of direct MC of fly ash with CO₂ captured by ash directly from flue gas with capacity of about 110 kg of CO₂ per t of ash is about 18 USD=15 €/t CO₂ [19, 20]. The cost of the MC per year is 0.42Mt*15€=6.3 M€. We consider that all mineral carbonation will take place at the Eesti PP, the largest PP in Estonia. OSA will be transported also from Auvere PP (1 km distance) and Balti PP (20.9 km distance). The cost of transportation by trucks of 0.07 Euro per km per ton of OSA is added to the total costs (Table 7). If the annual MC costs is 6.3 M€, OSA transport costs is 1.06 M€, then total annual MC costs is 7.36 M€. Possible revenues for CO₂ MC include: 1) avoided EEAP (40 Euro per t CO₂), 2) 3 € per t of OSA for OSA disposal, 3€*3.81 Mt=11.43 M € per year, 3) 28.6 Mt PCC produced per 30 years at the price of 50 € per t of high-quality PCC). Benefits from PCC production per year is 47.63 M€ per year, and 1428.8 M€ per 30 years. Total revenues per year: is 75.86 M€ and for 30 years 2275.65 M€. Total benefit for CO₂ MC is 69.56 M€ per year and for 30 years 2054.84 M€ (Table 7).

The total revenues for MC is 75.86 M€ per year at the price of EEAP 40€/t CO₂ and PCC price 50€/t. However,

considering total cost for MC of 7.36 M€, the MC process is becoming profitable at the lower prices of EEAP and PCC. The pure benefit of MC process is 69.56 M€ per years and 2054.84 M€ for 30 years for the EEAP price 40€/t CO₂ and PCC price 50€/ t. This balance could be changed considering possible variation of these prices at the market.

Table 7. CO₂ use revenues and costs for CO₂ mineral carbonation (MC) for three Eesti Energia Power Plants.

Plant	Parameters	Eesti Energia Power Plants			Total for 3 plants
		Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	
CO ₂ emissions produced per year, Mt		3.43	0.65	0.92	5.00
Oil shale ash produced per year, Mt		2.61	0.50	0.70	3.81
CO ₂ used for MC, Mt		0.47	0.00	0.00	0.42
CO ₂ avoided using MC		0.42	0.00	0.00	0.42
MC costs per year, M€		6.30	0.00	0.00	6.30
OSA transport costs to Eesti PP per year, M€		0.00	0.035	1.026	1.060
Total cost per year		6.30	0.035	1.026	7.360
Total cost per 30 years		189.00	1.04	30.77	220.81
EEAP per year (40 € per t CO ₂), M€		16.80	0.00	0.00	16.80
Oil Shale Ash Disposal Tax per year, (3 €/t), M€		7.84	1.49	2.1	11.43
Precipitated CaCO ₃ produced per year, Mt		0.65	0.12	0.18	0.95
Revenue for PCC per year (50€/ t) , M€		32.67	6.19	8.76	47.63
Total revenues per year, M€		57.31	7.68	10.87	75.86
Total revenues per 30 years, M€		1719.35	230.31	325.98	2275.65
Balance per year (revenues minus costs), M€		51.01	7.68	10.87	69.56
Balance per 30 years, M€		1530.35	229.27	295.21	2054.84

7.5 Total costs and benefits of CCUS scenario

Table 8. Economic results for CO₂ transport and storage scenario, M€ (* total for 3 Eesti Energia plants).

Company	Plant	Heidel- berg Cement	Eesti Energia (Enefit Energia)			VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latv- energo	Total for Estonian- Latvian scenario
		KNC	Eesti PP	Auvere PP	Balti PP	North PP		TEC-2 PP	
Pipeline		62.48		609.78*		83.73	755.99	28.51	784.5
Booster pumps		0.65	3.5	0.77	1.09	0.8	6.81	1.06	7.88
Wells		1.07	5.78	1.27	1.8	1.33	11.25	1.75	13
Facilities		0.37	2.02	0.44	0.63	0.46	3.93	0.61	4.54
Bare Erected Cost (BEC)		64.57		627.1*		86.32	777.98	31.93	809.92
On-cost		25.83		250.8*		34.53	311.19	12.77	323.97
Total Plant Cost		81.7		793.3*		109.2	984.1	40.4	1024.5
Decom Cost		16.14		156.77*		21.58	194.50	7.98	202.48

In the TPC of CO₂ transport and storage the most expensive part is transport costs, considering six project partners, long transport distances and need of both local (individual) and common pipelines. On-cost is additional 40% of the BEC and DC is 25% of TPC. Drilling of wells, booster pumps and storage facilities are the less expensive costs which

is only 3.1% from the BEC (Table 9). Analysis of the total balance for the Baltic CCUS scenario shows that project is beneficial at the proposed EEAP (40 €/t CO₂) and possible cost of 50 Euro for PCC (produced during CO₂ MC). However, detailed results show (Table 10), that the CCUS scenario will be beneficial only for Eesti Energia plants and for Latvenergo TEC-2. However, if the benefit is supported by CO₂ use for Eesti Energia, the reason of benefit for Latvian PP is explained by relative small transport distance and correspondingly low total cost for T&S per/t CO₂ injected (5.54 €). For the KNC and VKG Energia plants the balance will be close to zero at the EEAP of about 48 and 49.4 € correspondingly.

Table 9. Total economic results for CO₂ use, transport and storage scenario (* total for 3 Eesti Energia plants).

Company	Heidelberg Cement	Eesti Energia	VKG Energia	Total for 5 Estonian plants	Latvenergo	Total
Plant	KNC	Eesti Energia PPs	North PP		TEC-2 PP	Estonian-Latvian scenario
COSTtotal (T&S), €/t CO ₂	18.02	21.06*	19.36	20.54	5.54	18.38
COSTtotal (T&S) for 30 years, M€	264.87	2584.1*	354.2	3204.9	134.5	3313.4
Revenues for EEAP, M€	588	4908*	732	6240	972	7212
Pure benefit for CO ₂ MC, M€		2054*				
Total revenues, M€	588	6962*	732	8282.2	972	9254.2
Cost for CO ₂ capture and compression (25.5+2.8 € per t CO ₂), M€	441.18	3653.7*	548.5	4643.3	724.3	5367.6
Balance per 30 years (revenues-costs), M€	-118.1	724.4*	-170.7	434	113.2	547.2
Balance per one year (revenues-costs), M€	-4.94	24.2*	-5.69	14.47	3.77	18.44
EEAP needed for zero balance, €	48.0		49.4			

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The most sensitive parameters for the proposed scenario is EEAP and the market price of the PCC. At the proposed 40 and 50€/t for these parameters correspondingly, the total CCUS scenario, Eesti Energia PPs and Latvian TEC2 PP have positive balance. For the HeidelbergCement KNC and VKG Energia the higher EEAP is needed. These is explained by large distance from the storage site, CO₂ flow less than 1 Mt per year, and absent CO₂ use options, explained by the fact that these plants are already using their produced OSA either for cement production at KNC, or for other purposes at the VKG Energia plant.

In the previous studies the TPC in Australia for CO₂ transport, injection and monitoring varies in the limits of 3.4-9.5€/t CO₂ injected for cases involving short transport distances to storage formations with good characteristics. The TPC can reach almost 48€/t CO₂ injected for cases involving the transport of small volumes of CO₂ over long distances to storage formations with poorer characteristics [5]. In our previous study the T&S cost per one t of CO₂ avoided was 8.3€/t CO₂ injected, but it did not include monitoring costs and additional booster pump before injection and was planned for the larger CO₂ flow of 10.7 Mt per year and for scenario with two large PPs [4]. The total average T&S cost of the present scenario is 18.4€/t CO₂ injected. T&S is the most expensive for the Eesti Energia PPs with the largest transport distance, and the lowest transport and storage cost of 5.54€/t CO₂ injected is estimated for the less distant Latvenergo TEC2 PP.

In general our results are corresponding to the conclusions of the previous studies. Total T&S costs increase with increasing distance and are higher for the smaller CO₂ flow [5]. Participating in clusters is beneficial for smaller emitters, as they are sharing transport, compression, storage and monitoring costs. To improve economics of CCS, any possible CO₂ use options could be beneficial. Additional market studies are needed for the price of the PCC, as

its cost depends on the quality of the final product, which is highly variable at the market and could be cheaper, but also much more expensive, depending on the market needs and location. Wells drilling, CO₂ injection and monitoring costs are significantly cheaper compared to the transport costs for long distances. In case of additional market needs the old oil shale ash available in Estonian terricons could be additionally used for CO₂ MC. The first project for CO₂MC of 1Mt of OSA is under development in Estonia by TalTech researchers and Ragn-Sells company.

Conclusions:

- The Estonian-Latvian transboundary CCUS scenario includes cluster of six largest CO₂ producers, including cement plant and five PPs from Estonia and Latvia.
- Annually 6.8 Mt CO₂ could be captured, transported and injected, including 6 Mt CO₂ avoided using transport and storage and 0.42 Mt avoided using MC of Estonian OSA. During 30 years nearly 204 Mt CO₂ will be captured, used and stored, while 193 Mt CO₂ could be avoided.
- CCUS scenario includes MC of 0.42 Mt CO₂ from flue gas produced at Eesti PP and using 3.8 Mt of fresh OSA produced during combustion of OS at three Eesti Energia PP. OSA will be transported from Auvere and Balti PPs to MC plant using trucks.
- 6.3 Mt of captured and compressed CO₂ will be transported annually for onshore CO₂ storage site in Latvia (North Blidene) via pipelines. Small pipelines of 120-250 mm diameter from plants and one large common pipeline of 710 km length and 700 mm diameter will be constructed during two years of construction period.
- CO₂ will be injected into the 50 m thick Cambrian Deimena Formation reservoir sandstones at the depth of 1035-1150 m with 370-850 mD permeability. Four injection and two monitoring wells are planned. Monitoring program will start with baseline research before injection and will be repeated according to EU CCS regulations every year, and in the post-injection period during 30 years (in total 40 monitoring campaigns).
- The total average transport and storage cost of the scenario is 18.4 €/tCO₂ injected. This cost depends on the transport distance, according to the applied methodology, and it is the most expensive for the Eesti Energia PPs. The lowest T&S cost of 5.54 €/tCO₂ injected will have Latvenergo TEC-2 PP located at the smaller distance from storage site.
- At the price of EEAP of 40 €/t CO₂ and 50 €/t PCC the CCUS scenario could be beneficial for three Eesti Energia and Latvenergo TEC-2 PPs. For the KNC and VKG Energia plants without CO₂ use options, the higher EEAP of about 48-50 €/t CO₂ is needed to cover all CCUS costs including capture, compression, T&S and monitoring.

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